

Before school education organization 4 K skills in educators formation

Ravshanova Xafiza Komilovna - Sam vil PYMO' MM teacher .

+998996235311 khafizakomilovna@gmail.com

Abstract : This in the article before school education organization educators education and education process time demand based on organize reach for need future , 21st century skills and him of formation necessity and methods open given

Key words : Education , 4K skills , educator , communicative , critical thinking , collaboration , communication , child, creativity .

B trace we know that young people of our future , of our country foundation . Preschool education is the foundation of personality formation. Because during this period, the child needs special attention because it is the stage of understanding the world under the mind, restoring the foundations of imagination and knowledge. From this point of view, we should use modern educational technologies and modern approaches in educating preschool children. The "4K" model is a modern approach to the education system, and the use of the 4K model in the modern education system is aimed at children's critical thinking, free expression of their opinions, comprehensive development of preschool children, four main competencies includes. In order to form creativity, critical thinking, collaboration and communication skills in preschool children, it is necessary to develop these skills in the educators of the preschool education organization themselves. First, let's talk about what the 4K model is.

The development of technologies, globalization, demographic problems in the world are actively changing society. In today's era of globalization, the knowledge and skills of education developed in the last century are not enough to succeed in our time. The education system is also re-examining its goals and increasingly including a wide range of skills in its curricula. The most important are social skills, critical thinking, cooperation, problem solving . The main international document in the field of education adopted by UNESCO describes the "sustainable development goals" and defines

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-5

cognitive, social-emotional and behavioral learning outcomes. In the last few years, the educational system around the world, especially in primary education, has moved from a non-traditional direction in the formation of knowledge and skills, creating conditions for the development of modern competencies and skills of the 21st century. is being used. Despite the different rules of these skills in the various skills and educational outcomes of the 21st century, their set remains quite stable. In addition to existing skills or literacy, it lays the foundation for 21st century skills, which include "innovative skills"—the many skills of critical thinking and problem solving, creativity and innovation, communication, and collaboration. got rin.

Creativity is the ability of a person to come out of problematic situations in a unique way through thinking, to approach them creatively. Creativity concept (lot, ing . "create" - create , "creative" creator , creator) English from the language translation when you do creativity the meaning means For real while new , original (to himself characteristic) further polished material and spiritual dependencies is to create . Creativity to creativity aspiration to life creative approach to himself constant critical look put and analysis reach to say can Current time psychology and pedagogy to dictionary names based on of the teacher creativity his in his opinion , in communication , separately activity kind of creative to approach , to know defined as level to give can His at the core originality , practicality , unusualness and freedom lies Also creative thinking one to something different from the side to approach means Har how human being at birth creative ability with to the world will come . Him which to the road orientation and development educator undertake is loaded . So , until school education organizations in pupils creative ability to develop attention focus perfect generation educate support point be service does

Creative method passed The subject is full of child mastery with together , creativity also develops the ability . That's why for from the educator own science on the surface deep to knowledge have to be with together , in education efficient method and

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-5

awareness of methods Demand is enough Because future new innovations and of inventions all of them exactly creative competence through to the body will come .

"Communicativeness" The concept of " communication " . differently definitions there is . *Communication* two or from him more than people between to know or affective evaluation feature have has been information in exchange their mutually influence as is defined . Or : *communication* - people in the middle cooperation activity out of need surface coming and information exchange , mutual of influence the only one the way work exit , other the person perception to do and from understanding consists of has been connections installation and of development complex , wide comprehensive process . This is the concept of " communication " . the most complete and sure is the definition .

Critical thinking the term International terminology in the system Greek " *critical* " form of thinking as will be conducted ." *Kritikos* " " criticism " , " evaluation " , " examination " and others many p meaningful from the word come came out ; this the concept of " criticism " here diary the meaning of " accusation " in life doesn't mean , maybe mental ability the meaning means and " evaluation " , " determination " , " judgment" . make " , " separate like " ability " . to meanings have Critical of thinking intellectual The basics and etymology are very good ancient to the times go is worn

Critical thinking Richard W. Paul by two wavy movement as described (1994). Critical of thinking " first wave " is often " critical analysis , criticism own into received pure , reasonable called thinking.His details to him appeal those who did between difference does Barry According to K. Beyer (1995). according to , critical thinking clear , reasonable judgment release means Critical thinking in the process ideas provable , complete seeing output and assessment need Critical thinking abilities according to USA National council critical thinking as follows defines : " observation , experience , reasoning conduct , comments or communication through collected or harvest done information belief and which directs action (conceptualization) . to concepts active and

skillfully conversion , application , analysis make , synthesis to do or of assessment intellectual , advanced process as is determined .

Collaboration - Collective work skill - cooperation is the skill of working in a team. Accept help, take someone else's point of view, stand up for yourself when doing a task. In a word, try to work cooperatively. Collaborative work involves a group of people working together to achieve a common goal and achieve a set goal under any circumstances.

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of the 4K model in the educational process of preschool educational organizations leads to the following results: enriches the learning process of children; provides children with cognitive information (education to expand the range of knowledge about the environment, to develop cognitive needs); makes children eager to learn the material; expands opportunities for children to form their own personal knowledge and worldviews; increases the efficiency of two-way exchange of information; provides children with the necessary knowledge to prepare for independent life; promotes positive interactions between groups of different cultures and socio-economic levels; cooperation is such a situation that the subjects of the educational process work together, friendship, mutual help, community come to the surface. As a result, the order of the society will be fulfilled - we will train literate personnel who are competitive, ready to cooperate, understand problems in various life situations and boldly start to solve them, believe in the power of thinking, express independent opinions in the team, defend their opinions and views. Effective use of the 4K model is more important as it not only develops the young generation, who are the owners of our future, but also aims to form in them the skills necessary for successful adaptation to modern society.

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